

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17092047

Understanding The Scourge Of Drug Addiction: Perceptions Of Secondary School Students In Ika South LGA, Delta State

¹Mormah Felicia Ofuma & ²Kiyem Vivien Wamari

¹Department of Education Administration and Planning ,
Faculty of Education

University of Delta, Agbor, Nigeria

felicia.mormah@unidel.edu.ng; felymor2017@gmail.com +2348033596698

²Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology,
Central Hospital, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria
vivienkiyen@gmail.com; +2348064078540

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the perceptions of secondary school students on the scourge of drug addiction in Ika South Local Government Area, Delta State. Drug addiction among adolescents has emerged as a serious social and academic problem, negatively impacting students' performance, behavior, and future aspirations. Using a survey research design, data were collected from a randomly selected sample of 185 senior secondary school students (SS1–SS3) across six public schools. A structured 15-item questionnaire based on a 4-point Likert scale was used to gather information on the causes, effects, and possible solutions to drug addiction. The study revealed that factors such as broken homes, peer pressure, depression, and the desire for prestige are major contributors to drug abuse among students. The consequences include poor academic performance, involvement in social vices such as cultism and theft, and strained family relationships. Respondents recommended counseling, community rehabilitation centers, school clubs, and national drug surveys as effective solutions. Statistical analysis using mean, standard deviation, and t-tests confirmed no significant difference in responses between male and female students. The findings highlight the urgent need for stakeholders—parents, educators, government agencies, and health professionals—to address drug addiction among secondary school students through coordinated intervention programs.

Keywords: Drug addiction, secondary school, peer pressure, academic performance, intervention strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Social upheaval has become nothing to the youths of the society in this contemporary decades and it affected social development of the state. The activities carried out by most of the youths caused distraction and violence especially when it comes to political position. The emancipation of this violence and distraction lead on the political leaders, community leaders, youth's leaders as well as academic authorities today. However, majority of the citizens are engaged in society or the other depending on the kind of peers group they associate with in the environment they live. Drugs are commonly used by both young and old in any society. However, drugs are not just useful for human beings alone, but are also useful to animals for good and healthy living. Drug is an effective substance that can be used to cure sickness and to make life healthy. It is pertinent to note that drugs are used for beneficent therapeutic purposes, and is effective for good health; but abused by young people most

especially the students. They use it illegally and unlawfully, thus it becomes harmful to their bodies (Akintoye, 2022). Social effects may be reflected in an individual's enhanced tendency to engage in conflicts with friends, teachers, and school authorities. Cognitive effects of drugs relate to the individual's lack of concentration on academic work and memory loss. Lewinso (2017) defines a drug as any product other than food or water that affects the way people feel, think, see, and behave.

Drug addiction is the wrong use of drugs for purposes other than medical reasons, thus affecting the individual in a negative way socially, cognitively or physically. It is a substance that due to its chemical nature affects physical, mental and emotional functioning. It can enter the body through chewing, inhaling, smoking, drinking, rubbing on the skin or injection. Drug addiction is responsible for lost gross, destruction of property, bad health and broken homes. It is a dilemma which affects all parents, teachers, government officials, workers and the entire society (Bellow, 2021).

Drug misuse has become a global problem affecting many people. Addiction leads many young people into downhill of hopelessness that in some cases ends fatally. They range from teenage bliss users, to hard core heroin and cocaine addicts. Drug addiction has negative consequence for the individual and the society at large. Some of these drugs include; marijuana, cocaine, herionniectine, tramadol e.t.c these have a similar structure to chemical messenger called neurotransmitter, which are naturally produced by the brain and also it allows the drug to fill the brain, receptors and active nerve cells to send abnormal message. As a person or students continue to addict to drugs, the brain adapt to the overwhelming surges in producing less receptor in the reward circuit. Drug addiction has been a serious problem to the socio economic development of Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State.

The excessive use of harmful substance among students has become a subject of public concern to the government, nongovernmental organization (NGOs) cultural and religious groups, scientist, medical doctors, social scientist and researchers from different profession to find lasting solution to the problem. Drug addiction is a chronic, often relapsing brain disease that causes pain and damages to compulsive drug users despite the harmful consequences of drug addict. Drug addiction is a brain disease because the abuse of drug leads to a change in the structure and function of the brain. It is because of this change in the brain that it is so challenging for a person who is addicted to stop abusing drugs.

Based on this, researcher view mostly lies on considering the level of cultism among students, armed robbery, rape, spread of HIV, truancy, educational decay, killing, kidnapping in the large society. One can say that it was as a result of excess drug addictions that lead secondary school students into such crime. The intention of the AU was established on 25 May 1963 in Addis Ababa by 32 signatory governments; the OAU was disbanded on 9 July 2002. The most important decisions of the AU are made by the Assembly of the African Union, a semi-annual meeting of the heads of state and government of its member states. The organization held seminar on the problems of drug addiction in Lagos, 2022, and declared that "Drug addiction that are broadly prevalent in African countries have continued to increase. These problems affect the individual, the family and the society in general. Substance abuse, which was originally conceived as the problem of a selected few is today becoming a problem of a sizeable proportion of the world population.

Unlawful Drug traffic generates huge profit and that is the major reason why it has been very difficult to fight against drug traffic in spite of several laws that have been promulgated. Drug addiction constitute a serious threat to the survival and effective functioning of human societies, lives are lost daily through addiction and activities of addicts. A significant number of deaths from accidents and violent crimes have been traced to the activities of persons under the influence of drugs. Excessive abuse of drug can cause physically or psychological dependence on individual. Also, it can bring conflict between the user and the society. It may lead to social problem and equally generate conflict within user and his social environment (Ejikeme 2019).

World Health Organisation (2019), said that drugs like alcohol, tobacco and cocaine are the root cause of road accident which have claimed lives and the high rate of sickness suffered by societies today. The issue of drug abuse has become the main theme of discussion in societies today. Drug addiction does not only destroy the affected person or individual but also have a negative effect on those that are connected to the individual. Indeed, drug addiction had become a challenging problem to the lives and success of the youth as it can be evidently not only as a source of sorrow to the parents, guardians and relatives but it is also a big challenge to the nation wholly.

Declining grades, absenteeism from school and other activities, and increased potential for dropping out of school are problems associated with adolescent substance abuse. Low level of commitment to education and higher truancy rates appear to be related to substance use among adolescents. Substance abuse can drain a family's financial and emotional resources (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2020).

The predicament is so grave that it has extended beyond the usual characteristic of abusers being male, adult, and urban-based to now include females, youngsters and those who live mostly in the northern part of Nigeria. Its economic effect is so upsetting that it is estimated that the annual retail cost of psychotropic drug by prescription is over two billion naira while the alcoholic company which produces over five billion gallons of alcoholic beverages annually generate more than four billion naira from sales to a consumer population of about 30-35 million people (Okoye, 2022).

The role of parents in curtailing the possibility of their children becoming addicted to hard drugs requires that they spend quality time with their family. Parents must discard the know-it-all attitude and give room for heart-to-heart discussions before decisions are taken or foisted on family members. Gap left in the study is that agencies like parents, teachers and government that is in position to punish drug addiction persons, are the one to protect those who engaged in the business. A teacher as educators has failed to educate the students about the harmful effect of using drugs.

Statement of the Problem

Student's involvement in drug addiction might cause effect on their academic dream either positive or negative. Drug addiction intorstigate student's attitude to art strange where ever they found themselves, they rape innocent girls. Most of them drop out of school because of the benefit of reward they attained. The effect of drug addiction affects students academic performance. Assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction has negative effect on secondary schools students. The intake of this drugs make student to active involved in wrongly way of their fellow students, disrespect their family, constitute distraction to teachers, the society as well as engaging themselves in different social clubs and organization such as cultism, stealing, drinking, womanizing, intimidating people in the society. Hence, the study examine Assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction on secondary schools students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State.

The main purpose of this study is to Assess of the perception and effects of drug addiction on secondary schools students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The specific objectives of the study are: (a) To determine cause of drug addiction on secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. (b) To examine the possible solution to assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction among secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State.

In line with the research objectives, the following hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on the causes of drug addiction among secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State while H₀₂: there is no significant difference between male and female students on the possible solution to assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction among secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State.

This study will be of benefit to State ministry of drugs agency to take adequate measure on how to tackle the excess usage of drugs addiction in the society. The result will be significant to educational administration to counsel the students on how to avoid themselves from perception of effect of drug addiction within and the environment they find themselves.

The study is important to the society as the home of the guidance and counseling for their children and students living within the implication of drugs addiction and negative effect and damage it cause to their education and wellbeing. The result of the empirical study will benefit postgraduates students on how to provide solution to the effects of drug addiction on secondary school students. The study is significant to post secondary school students as a guide for them to abstained from drug addiction. The study will benefit the parents e.t.c to be aware of the effects of drug addiction as well as helping those who directly indulge in drug abuse to come out of it in order to be profitable to themselves and the society at large. The study will help other researchers and book writer to encourage government drug agencies to inculcate law and order that will guide the citizens how to abstain from drug addiction.

The scope of this study is to examine Assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction on secondary schools students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The scope covered some selected senior secondary schools in the study area. It covered the four variables such as causes of drug addiction to senior secondary school students, effects of drug addiction to senior secondary schools students; possible solution to the assessment of the perception of effects of drug addiction among secondary school students and types of drug used by senior secondary school students.

The study is limited to some selected secondary in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. This study is geographically limited to selected secondary schools in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The study is also limited due to financial constrain that prevent the researcher from covering other schools for more materials that would enriched the study.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design used for this study was survey research design. A survey research is a systematic study of a sample from the population to discover the relative frequency, occurrence, distribution and interrelation of psychological and social variables (George, 2013). This research design was adopted to discover the effect of drug abuse among secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The population of the study covers nine hundred and ninety seven (997) male and female senior secondary schools in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The population consists of all the senior secondary school classes of SS 1, SS 2 and SS3. A simple random sampling technique was used to select one hundred and eighty five (185) students of public senior secondary schools in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The researcher picked the sample of SS 1, SS 2, and SS 3 male and female students randomly using observation method through the data gather from the Post Primary Education Board. The researcher selected six 6 senior secondary school out of the entire population. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into two sections. Section A collected personal information data. The section B was designed elicited information on drug abuse and its effect on the academic performance of secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. The questionnaire is fifteen (15) item instruments on a four point Likert scale of strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed. The questionnaire was scored on a 4 point to one scale.

The questionnaire was drafted by the researcher and hand over to the project supervisor for validation. The supervisor checked the instrument and made useful suggestion and correction. The questionnaire was designed on a 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The test-re-test method for reliability of research instrument and Cronbach Alpha test was used to know if the research instrument is reliable, yielding a Cronbach Alpha of 0.715 using Kuder–Richardson reliability coefficient method. Besides, the validity of research instrument was done via content validity by research supervisor. The questionnaire was administered to teachers and students of the sampled schools. The researcher employed two research assistance during the cause of this study. A total number of two hundred (200) questionnaires was administered and retrieved; the researchers passed vital information to respondents with regards to the whole exercise. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to determine the fitness of the data collection. The researcher also made use of t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant either to reject or not to reject. The benchmark says that any mean value of 2.50 and above justify that the null hypotheses is accepted while any mean value below 2.50 and above justify that the null hypotheses is rejected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What are the causes of drug addiction to secondary school students?*

Table 1 showing respondents responses on the causes of drug addiction to secondary school students

S/N O	Statements	(45) Male Students						(140) Female Students					
		SA 4	A 3	S 2	SD 1	\bar{x}	SD	SA 4	A 3	S 2	SD 1	\bar{x}	SD
1	Broken home lead students to drug abuse.	30	10	3	2	3.79	0.65	90	30	15	5	3.89	0.78
2	Students engage in drug abuse because of sexual intercourse	29	15	1	-	3.62	0.73	95	20	19	6	3.46	0.68
3	Students engage in drug due to depression, tension, insecurity.	29	16	-	-	3.64	0.73	99	31	6	4	3.61	0.72
4	Students go into drug abuse for prestigious reasons especially boys before their female counterparts	42	3	-	-	3.93	0.79	96	34	7	3	3.59	0.72
5	Students get addicted to drug especially when preparing for exams in order for them to stay awake	40	3	2	-	3.8	0.77	87	39	10	4	3.3	0.66
	Grand mean/Standard deviation					3.75	0.73					3.56	0.71

The data presented in table 1 shows that there is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the cause of drug addiction to secondary school students with the average mean of 3.73 and 3.56 and standard deviation of 0.73 and 0.71 which is above the decision rule of 2.50 that was stated.

Research Question 2: *What are the Possible Solution to Drug addiction used by used by secondary school students?*

Table 4 showing respondents responses on the possible solution to drug addiction used by secondary school students

S/NO	Statements	45 Male Students						140 Female Students					
		SA	A	S	SD	\bar{x}	SD	SA	A	S	SD	\bar{x}	SD
16	The students should be counseled on the negative effect of drug abuse	32	10	1	2	3.8	0.72	100	30	6	4	3.61	0.72
17	The state and national survey of patterns of drug should be carried out among youth in primary and secondary education.	39	5	-	1	3.80	0.77	91	40	6	3	3.56	0.71
18	Community rehabilitation centres should be created where drugs abuser can live together and share their problems in	31	10	2	2	3.56	0.71	80	35	20	5	3.36	0.69

	group												
19	Students should be encouraged to form and become member of useful club either in school or community	36	6	1	2	3.69	0.74	99	21	3	7	3.37	0.67
20	Principals and teachers should work together in educating the students on the implication of drug taking	39	5	-	1	3.82	0.76	93	27	15	5	3.49	0.79
	Grand mean/Standard deviation					3.73	0.73					3.48	0.71

The data presented and analyzed above in table 4 indicate that there is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the possible solution to drug addiction used by secondary school students with the average mean of 3.73 and 3.48 with a standard deviation of 0.73 and 0.71 which reveals that the instrument used for this study is reliable since the average mean is above the decision rule of 2.50 that was state.

4.4 Testing of Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response of male and female students on the causes of drug addiction used by secondary school students.

Table 5 showing t-score hypothesis tested on the cases of drug addiction to secondary school students.

GROUP	NO	\bar{x}	SD	DF	T/cal Value	Standard Error	T/critical value	Level of Significance	Decision
Male students	45	3.75	0.73	185-2 (183)	1.58	0.12	1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female Student	140	3.56	0.71						

From the above table the t-calculated value of 1.58 is lower than the t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore the null hypotheses which state that there is no significant difference was accepted since it is above the decision rule of 2.50 respectively

Table 8 showing t-score hypothesis tested on the possible solution to drug addiction used by secondary school students

GROUP	NO	\bar{x}	SD	DF	T/cal Value	T/critical value	Standard Error	Level of Significance	Decision
Male Students	45	3.73	0.73	183	2.08	1.96	0.12	0.05	Rejected
Female Students	140	3.48	0.71						

The hypotheses tested showed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on the possible solution to drug addiction used by secondary school students. From the above table, the t-calculated value of 2.08 is higher than the t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significant. Hence, the null hypothesis stated in the table above is rejected, since it is above the decision rule of 2.50.

4.5 Causes of Drug Abuse

The findings of the study shows that all the items stated in the table 1 are causes of drug abuse under research question 1. The study showed that broken home lead students to drug abuse, respondents strongly agreed that students engage in drug abuse because of sexual intercourse, while respondents agreed that students engage in drug due to depression, tension, insecurity. The finding showed that

students go into drug abuse for prestigious reasons especially boys before their female counterparts and respondents agreed that students get addicted to drug especially when preparing for exams in order for them to stay awake. This is in agreement with the assertion of Gilbert and Lombart (2020) who said that depression, tension, insecurity, feeling of inadequacy and difficulty lead students to engage on drugs abuse in most cases. Gilbert and Lombart further opined that students interpersonal relationship cause drug abuse and this affect academic behavior of secondary school student as well as preventing them from performing better in their study

Possible Solution to Drug Addiction by Secondary School Students

Finally the findings of the study show that all items stated on table iv are the possible solution to drug abuse. The findings showed that students should be counseled on the negative effect of drug abuse, respondents agreed that state and national survey of drug should be carried out among youth in primary and secondary education, respondents strongly agreed that community rehabilitation centres should be created where drugs abuser can live together and share their problems in group. Respondents strongly agreed that students should be encouraged to form and become member of useful club either in school or community while principals and teachers should work together in educating the students on the implication of drug taking. This is in agreement with Dikeh (2017) who suggested that state and national survey of drug use be carried out among students in primary and post-primary institution. Oikeh (2007) suggested that for the identification of students who use drugs and the different types of drugs used. In addition, he called principals and teachers to work with parents and welfare workers in educating the school or in the community. This is to help them use their lecture time wisely.

Summary of Findings

The aim of this study is to examine effect of drug abuse addiction on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State. Chapter one of the study considered background of the study, statement of the problem, purpose of the study, research questions and research hypotheses. The study reviewed concept of drugs, Drug abuse, Types of drugs, Causes of drug abuse, Effects of drug abuse and Solution to drug abuse. Chapter three considered research methodology survey research design, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, research instrument, validity of the study, reliability of the study, method of data collection and method of data analysis. A structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for collection of data. The questionnaire contained 15 items which was administered personally. Four-point Likert rating scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Kuder–Richardson reliability coefficient method of 0.715 which is in line with decision rule of 2.5 and above mean score used to determine the extent of agreement based on the findings

Findings

The data analyzed revealed that: Students who indulge in drug turnout to be truants, Broken home lead students to drug abuse. Students who used drugs in school often beat up their teachers and fellow students. Students who engage in drug turn out to be highway robbers. Community rehabilitation centres should be created where drugs abuser can live together and share their problems in group

CONCLUSION

Broken home, depression, feeling of inadequacy peers influence, social economic status of the family, inadequate academic security/supervision, loneliness and isolated life are causes of drug abuse. students interpersonal relationship cause drug abuse and this affect academic behavior of secondary school student as well as preventing them from performing better in their study. The identification of students who use drugs and the different types of drugs used. In addition, he called principals and teachers to work with parents and welfare workers in educating the school or in the community.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made (i) Students who indulge in drug should be advised to beware of the negative effects it has on their health. (ii) Students should be engaged in productive social activities both at school and at home so as to avert the temptation of being involved in drugs. (iii) Government should punish anyone find guilty of drug addiction in Nigeria society. (iv) Teachers and parents should advice students not to engage on drug addiction in order to achieve positive academic performance. (v) Student are encourage to

disassociate themselves from the use of drug addiction in order to pursuit good academic performance.

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